

A study to assess the effectiveness of structured nursing intervention on knowledge regarding emergency management of victim underwent road traffic accident among second year GNM nursing students of selected nursing college of Rajkot, Gujarat” in the year 2017”

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ABSTRACT

The study was conducted to assess the effectiveness of structured nursing intervention on knowledge regarding emergency management of victim underwent road traffic accident among diploma nursing students.

The study was conducted in Nursing College at Rajkot, Gujarat. Total samples were 30. Random purposive sampling technique was used. The research tool was developed in English after an extensive of literature and experts opinion. The structured questionnaire was used as an instrument to measure the level of knowledge of nursing students about road traffic accident at Rajkot.

This study revealed that samples had Good knowledge (86.66%) and very few of them adjusted in average category of knowledge (13.33%) in pre test study. Moreover, there were no any single respondent set in excellent category of knowledge.

Chi-square test was calculated to find out the association between the demographic variables and the level of knowledge regarding road traffic accident among diploma nursing students and it resulted there is association between the demographic variable e.g. age, witness of RTA and management of RTA care .

Keywords: *Effectiveness, RTA, Knowledge, STP, Nursing.*

Introduction:

First aid is an important skill. By performing simple procedures and following certain guidelines, it may possible to save lives by giving basic treatment until professional medical help arise Drivers to be trained in safety norms and emergency first-aid. A majority of the 6000 fatal accidents reported in the cities each year are avoidable if proper safety measures are taken. (Dr. Jimmy M.L)

Need for the Study

World health organization (WHO) its strategy of 2011 reports that currently road traffic injuries are the leading cause of deaths and injuries, the 10th leading cause of all deaths and 9th leading contributor to the burden of disease worldwide based on disability adjusted life years. The numbers of deaths resulting from road traffic crashes have been projected to reach 8.4 million in the year 2020. (WHO, 2000)

The chart of deaths occurring after road traffic accidents can be grouped into 3 peaks. First peak of death occurs immediately after the accidents. The major reason for death in this group is head injury. The second peak of death occurs in first four hours after the accidents. This period is called "GOLDEN HOUR" The main cause of death in golden hour is blood loss. The third peak of deaths occurs three weeks after the accidents. This is due to multi organ failure. If we can give correct first aid and shift the patients to the optimum hospital as early as possible, then we can reduce three fourths of R.T.A deaths and can also improve the quality of life obtained after the treatment completion of accident victims. (**The Hindu online edition of India's national news paper,tuesday,may10,2005**)

Larson e.m) Traffic crashes constitute a major, worldwide public-health problem that cause disabilities, life-long suffering, and huge economic losses. When a person is injured in a traffic crash, actions taken by bystanders often are of crucial importance. To perform first-aid actions in a correct manner, bystanders, often laypersons, need both the courage and the knowledge to do so. For preventive purposes, society spends large resources to inform and educate the public in order to enhance people's ability to take correct actions. A questionnaire was administered to 2,800 randomly selected persons aged 18-74 years. The response rate was 67.5%. During the previous five years, 39% of the population had received first-aid training

Objectives of the Study

1. To assess the pre-test level of knowledge regarding emergency management of victim underwent road traffic accident among second year GNM nursing students of selected nursing college of Rajkot, Gujarat"
2. To measure the post-test level of knowledge regarding emergency management of victim underwent road traffic accident among second year GNM nursing students of selected nursing college of Rajkot, Gujarat

3. To evaluate the effectiveness of structured nursing intervention in knowledge regarding emergency management of victim underwent road traffic accident among second year GNM nursing students of selected nursing college of Rajkot, Gujarat"
- ✓ To find the association between post test level of knowledge and selected socio-demographic variables of 2nd year GNM nursing.

HYPOTHESES

H_0 There will be no significance between pre-test and post-test and post test group score on emergency management of victim underwent road traffic accident.

H_1 There will be no significance between selected socio demographic variables and post test level of knowledge regarding emergency management of victim underwent road traffic accident among second year GNM nursing students.

Material and Methods:

Research design: Pre experimental design

Setting: The study was conducted in selected nursing college at Rajkot

Population: The target population and the accessible population were same for the present study i.e. Diploma Nursing students in an Indore Nursing college, Indore.

Sample: 30 samples

Sampling Technique: The Random purposive sampling technique

Data analysis: The demographic variables were organized by using descriptive measures (frequency and percentage).The association between the level of knowledge and the selected demographic variables were assessed by Chi-square test.

Result & Discussion**Table-1 Frequency & Percentage distribution of students by their demographic characteristics**

DEMOGRAPHIC VARIABLES	CHARACTARISTICS	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE
AGE	17-18 YEARS	2	6.66%
	19-20 YEARS	0	0
	21-22 YEARS	15	50%
	ABOVE 23	13	43.33%
SEX	MALE	7	23.33%
	FEMALE	23	76.66%
WITENESS OF RTA	YES	4	86.66%
	NO	26	13.33%
FIRST AID TRANING PROGRAMME	ONCE	6	20%
	TWICE	2	6.66%
	NEVER	22	73.33%
MANAGEMENT OF RTA CARE	YES	21	70%
	NO	9	30%

Majority of diploma nursing students were in the age group between 21-22 years (50%) followed above 23 years (43.33%) and 6.66% students were in age category between 17-18 years

Next in gender demographic variables, there is majority of diploma nursing students were females (76.66%) and minimal percentage of the sample was males (23.33%). In samples, 86.66% students witnessed for road traffic accident while 13.33% students were not.

Beside, many students about 73.33% didn't get first aid training never and 20% were trained once and 6.66% were trained twice.

Lastly, about 70% students know the management of RTA while 30% didn't know about same.

In this present study the mean and standard deviation in pre test assessment score was **12.64**, (**SD=2.01**) and in post test assessment mean score was 17.06, (**SD=0.86**). The result shows that the STP is effective and helpful to raise the knowledge.

In the association between socio-demographic variables and pre-test knowledge of Nursing students in relation to the age, witness of RTA and management of RTA care the chi-square value obtained ($X^2=0.57 < P=0.95 < 0.05, df=2$), ($X^2=0.52 < P=0.99 < 0.05, df=1$) and ($X^2=0.40 < P=0.99 < 0.05, df=1$).

Conclusion

This study reveals that majority of the nursing students have adequate knowledge and regarding RTA after implementation of STP in nursing college at Rajkot.

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